

Pleomorphic adenoma of palatal minor salivary glands: A case report

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Abstract

Minor salivary gland tumors (MSGTs) are a varied group of tumours with a wide range of histological features and growth patterns. Early diagnosis is necessary to determine the tumour's clinical behaviour and any potential dentoalveolar implications, which is challenging to do. We present a case of a 36-year-old male patient with a chief complaint of non-tender palatal swelling that progressively enlarged over six years. After a detailed history and clinical examination, the provisional diagnosis was given as a benign tumour of the palatal minor salivary gland, which was confirmed after radiographic evaluation and histopathological tests, and a precise diagnosis was given as a pleomorphic adenoma(PA) of palatal minor salivary gland. Thus, this report explains the patient's clinical history, presentation, radiographic and histological results, as well as a literature evaluation to establish the importance of its diagnosis and the therapeutic plan.

Keywords: Pleomorphic adenoma, Benign tumor, Minor salivary gland

Introduction

Salivary gland neoplasms represent 3–5% of the entire head and neck neoplasms and fewer than one percent of all tumours. Minor salivary gland tumors (MSGTs) are rare, making up ten to fifteen percent of all salivary gland tumours (SGT). Tongue (5%), floor of mouth (5%), cheek mucosa (12%), lips (15%), and palate (50%) are where they are most commonly seen. Numerous categories have been created because of their enormous variation and the absence of standard criteria, making it challenging to establish a sufficient clinical-histological association. ^[1] Benign SGTs are a broad category of neoplasms that exhibit a variety of clinical manifestations. Several recently identified benign tumours were added in the World Health Organisation's fifth edition of its classification for salivary gland tumours in 2022. ^[2] Clinical history, physical examination, and supplementary methods such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), computed tomography (CT) and fine needle aspiration biopsy (FNAB) are used for diagnosis. A provisional diagnosis that needs to be verified by the

relevant intraoperative histopathology analysis. If we fail to do complete surgical excision, MSGTs have a high recurrence risk (5-30%). Compared to 65% of all malignant lesions, 6% of benign small salivary gland tumours are thought to relapse.^[1]

Case Presentation

Primary complaint of a 36-year-old male patient who visited the Department of Oral Medicine and Radiology was swelling in the hard palate region for six years. Six years ago, he visited a dental specialist and was advised few investigations, after which surgery was planned for the same by a consultant. As swelling was not associated with pain, patient did not undergo any treatment. Patient presented again due to progressive swelling, causing difficulty in mastication and speech. Patient had no history of any systemic illness or allergies. His past medical and dental history was not contributory. On physical examination no abnormality was seen. All systems and vitals were within normal limits.

Extraoral examination

Bilateral facial symmetrical, lips were competent, bilaterally synchronous movements were seen with TMJ, muscles of mastication were nontender, and no lymph node was palpable.

Intraoral examination

Single localised swelling was seen on anterior hard palate on right side, crossing the midline. Extending anteroposteriorly from palatal rugae till posterior border of hard palate, mediolaterally from 0.5 cm left to midline till marginal gingiva and superoinferiorly from palatal vault till 0.5 cm below occlusal plane of right molars. Pink in colour, roughly oval, measuring approximately 5*3 cm in diameter. Edge was clearly defined with smooth surface. Visible pulsations were absent. (Figure 1).

Figure 1 : Intraoral photographs of area of interest

All inspectory findings were confirmed on palpation. Margins were smooth with firm consistency. Tenderness, bleeding, fixity, and translucency were absent. Swelling was not fluctuant, non-compressible, or non-reducible. PA, hyperplasia of minor salivary gland, and adenoid cystic carcinoma were the differential diagnoses given. Occlusion Radiograph was

taken of the maxilla. In which no palatal bone involvement was seen. CBCT—cone beam computed tomography—was performed with an 8*8 FOV. In axial view, a soft tissue shadow was appreciated in the palatal region of the upper right teeth. No bone involvement was seen with hard palate. (Figure 2,3)

Figure 2 : Axial view showing soft tissue shadow

Figure 3 : Cross sectional view of 25

USG—Ultrasonography of hard palate was performed using high frequency transducer. In which a well-defined heterogeneously isoechoic lesion of approximately 2.6×2×1.8 cm was noted on hard palate predominantly on right side with internal vascularity and palatal bone erosion suggestive of most probably minor salivary gland lesion. Further evaluation by CT scan and biopsy was suggested to rule out possibility of malignancy. CBCT showed no bony involvement, whereas USG suggested palatal bone erosion, prompting further evaluation with CT. CT—Relatively well defined isodense soft tissue attenuation lesion was noted along the hard palate, appeared to be arising from mucosa with convexity towards oral cavity

measuring 1.6×1.2×1.1 cm. The lesion showed smooth margins, no calcification. It did not involve the adjacent bone. On post contrast study it did not show any enhancement. Multiple homogenously enhancing enlarged lymph nodes were noted at level I and IIa region bilaterally largest of size 1.1×0.6 cm on right side with maintained fatty hilum. All these imaging features were suggestive of soft tissue lesion arising from the mucosa along the hard palate likely of neoplastic etiology. Histology–H&E and PAP stained showed RBCs throughout the smear & few acute inflammatory cells, neutrophils. Features were inconclusive therefore further investigations were advised. FNAC–Smears were cellular, showing clusters & sheets of epithelial cells. Cells were round to ovoid containing a lot of cytoplasm and nuclei positioned eccentrically (plasmacytoid), having dull nuclear chromatin that is coarsely granular. Spindle shape myoepithelial cells were also seen. The background contained scant fibrillary chondromyxoid stroma. Thus, the cytological features were suggestive of cellular pleomorphic adenoma. Hence, final diagnosis was given as PA of minor salivary glands on hard palate.

Management

After the diagnosis all necessary blood tests were done and under stringent aseptic circumstances local anesthesia, lesion was totally excised. Flaps were sutured, patients were prescribed medication and was instructed to prevent pressure or injury at surgery site. (Figure 4)

Figure 4 : Incision and Reflection

Follow up

Weekly professional prophylactics were performed throughout first month and again at 4-month intervals. No recurrence or any unpleasant symptoms were noted. Operative site showed good healing.

Discussion

Parotid, submandibular, and sublingual are the three pairs of major salivary glands. While the small glands are seen on the tongue, the palate, the cheeks and the lips.^[3] In a review by Olivia Pons Vicente et al., the authors claim that 65–80% of total MSGTs are found in the palatal area. According to their analysis, the posterior portion of the hard palate (33.2%) was where MSGTs were most frequently found; next up were soft palate (16.7%), upper lip mucosa (16.7%), cheek mucosa (11.1%), and retromolar trigone (11.1%). Therefore, 94.1% of all MSGTs of palate were benign. Most prevalent benign histological type, accounting for 55.3% of cases, was PA. ^[1] PA is a mixed benign tumor. Because of its morphological diversity and differentiation of tumour cells differ among tumours and within the same tumour, they are termed as "mixed tumour". Occurrence is typically between 4th-6th decades, although can also occur in children and young adults with minor female preference. ^[4]

A painless, slow-growing, and firm smooth, dome-shaped tumour, is often encountered on posterior lateral portion of palate. Hard palate mucosa seems to be fixed due to its close-knit structure. Patients life style and health may be hampered due to decreased nutrition and low social confidence as he or she might experience difficulty in speech and mastication.

Benign mixed tumours appear on CT as a roughly round, homogenous lesion with a higher density than surrounding glandular tissue. Calcifications inside the tumour are frequently observed. Dark patches or foci with low signal intensity in MRI typically indicate dystrophic calcifications or fibrosis. Benign mixed tumour is the preferred diagnosis if there is calcification (signal void); otherwise, it is challenging to distinguish it from other parotid masses. On scintigraphy a chilly spot is seen. ^[5]

Microscopically, capsule appears dense but is nearly always incomplete. Strands, sheets, and ducts of dark-staining epithelial cells are visible. "Myxoid" stroma is made up of scattered cells in matrix. Occasionally keratin production foci are seen. ^[6]

Surgical excision is recognized treatment . Rarely, an intraosseous PA originating from ectopic salivary tissue may occur. Primary tumor's inadequate removal and seeding can cause recurrence. Long-standing, untreated tumours or recurring ones may turn malignant. Term "carcinoma ex pleomorphic adenoma" refers to these uncommon malignant tumours.^[4] Thus this case report emphasises the need of an early diagnosis as it negatively impacts patient's

overall health and way of life by impairing speech and mastication, resulting in poor oral hygiene and nutrition, and raising the risk of oral infections and malignant transformation.

Conclusion

Despite being a rare benign tumour of the minor salivary glands, it is significant because of its consequences, which include speech and mastication difficulties, poor oral hygiene and nutrition, and an increased risk of oral infections, all of which can negatively impact the affected person's overall health. Thus this case report provides a insight for the need of early diagnosis and the crucial role of the history taking, physical examination and all the necessary investigation in it.

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